

Synthesis and characterization of some isothiocyanato complexes of dioxotungsten(VI) with morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands

M. S. Pathania, Ashiq Hussain, H. N. Sheikh* and B. L. Kalsotra

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 006, India

E-mail : hnsheikh@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 17 August 2004, revised 22 March 2005, accepted 11 April 2005

Isothiocyanato complexes of dioxotungsten(VI) with morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands have been prepared by the reaction of tetrakisothiocyanatodioxotungsten(VI) anion with corresponding ligand in aqueous medium in presence of HCl. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, IR, electronic spectra, magnetic moment and conductivity measurements in addition to thermal gravimetric analysis TGA/DTA.

Dioxotungsten(VI) complexes with Schiff bases and chelating ligands are limited. They are mostly organometallics and a few studies on dioxotungsten(VI) complexes of chelating ligands have been reported¹. Isothiocyanato complexes of dioxotungsten(VI) with some biologically active chelating ligands and other Schiff bases have also been synthesized and characterized^{2,3}. The complexes of morpholinomethyl urea and morpholinomethyl thiourea with divalent transition metals viz. Co^{II} and Cu^{II} and some rare earth metals have been extensively studied in respect of their bonding, thermal and magnetic behaviour⁴. The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of some isothiocyanato complexes of dioxotungsten(VI) with morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands using [WO₂(NCS)₄]²⁻ as precursors³.

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic results (Tables 1–3) showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with general formulae [WO₂(SCN)₂L-L] where L-L = morpholinomethyl urea (MMU), morpholinomethyl thiourea (MMTU), piperidinomethyl urea (PMU), piperidinomethyl thiourea (PMTU), pyrrolidinomethyl urea (PylMU) and pyrrolidinomethyl thiourea (PylMTU). All the complexes are coloured, stable in air, insoluble in common organic solvents but fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of all the complexes exhibit bands in the region 860–880 and 935–958 cm⁻¹ due to the ν_{as} (O=W=O) and ν_s (O=W=O) modes respectively, indicating the presence of *cis*-WO₂ structure⁵. Three bands for ν (CN), ν (CS) and ν (NCS) were observed in the spectra of the complexes

at 2065–2070, 758–810 and 471–496 cm⁻¹ respectively suggesting that the thiocyanate is N-bonded⁶. Moreover, the ν (C=O) absorption band at 1655–1660 cm⁻¹ in the free MMU, PMU and PylMU and ν (C=S) modes of MMTU, PMTU and PylMTU at 1295–1310 cm⁻¹ and 770–785 cm⁻¹ are lowered by 20–30 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen (O) or thiocarbonyl sulphur (S) in bonding with the metal. The ν (C–N–C) mode of morpholine, piperidine or pyrrolidine ring around 1120–1165 cm⁻¹ shows a negative shift in the complexes indicating the involvement of ring nitrogen in bonding with tungsten. There is also negative shift in stretching and bending modes of N–H bands of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine ring in complexes which indicates involvement of ring nitrogen in W–N bond formation. A slight positive shift in (C–O–C) stretching mode of morpholine ring shows that morpholine ring does not involve its oxygen atom in bond formation with tungsten.

These IR bands suggest that in all the complexes the ligands behave in bidentate chelating mode coordinating the metal through carbonyl (O) or thiocarbonyl (S) and the ring nitrogen.

Conductance and magnetic measurements : The observed molar conductance of these complexes in 10⁻³ M DMF are in the range of 18–28 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹, which indicates the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for dioxotungsten(VI) complexes.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra (Table 2) of the complexes exhibit two spectral peaks in the region 470–490 and 610–650 nm. The first intense peak may be due to ligand to metal charge transfer transitions. The second peak

Table 1. Analytical data and some physical properties of the synthesized dioxotungsten(VI) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex (Empirical formula, mol. wt.)	Color	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Found (Calcd.) %					λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) (DMF)
				C	H	N	S	W	
1.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMU] (WC ₈ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂) (491.19)	Light yellow	221	19.50 (19.56)	2.58 (2.66)	14.31 (14.25)	13.00 (13.05)	37.46 (37.42)	18
2.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMTU] (WC ₈ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₃) (507.26)	Light yellow	218	18.90 (18.94)	2.54 (2.58)	13.82 (13.80)	18.90 (18.96)	36.23 (36.24)	12
3.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMU] (WC ₉ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂) (489.22)	Greenish yellow	242	22.06 (22.09)	3.08 (3.09)	14.26 (14.31)	13.10 (13.10)	37.56 (37.57)	13
4.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMTU] (WC ₉ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₃) (505.28)	Light green	232	21.35 (21.39)	2.81 (2.99)	13.88 (13.86)	18.97 (19.03)	36.42 (36.38)	16
5.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMU] (WC ₈ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂) (475.19)	Yellow	223	20.15 (20.22)	2.68 (2.75)	14.72 (14.73)	13.41 (13.49)	38.76 (38.68)	17
6.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMTU] (WC ₈ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₃) (491.25)	Golden yellow	216	19.47 (19.55)	2.62 (2.66)	14.20 (14.25)	19.42 (19.58)	37.48 (37.42)	14

Table 2. Electronic spectra of dioxotungsten(VI) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	L → M CT nm (ϵ^a)	L → L CT nm (ϵ^a)
1.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMU]	484 (2379)	635 (418)
2.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMTU]	480 (2192)	630 (437)
3.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMU]	490 (1943)	650 (326)
4.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMTU]	485 (1979)	641 (397)
5.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMU]	475 (2238)	622 (461)
6.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMTU]	470 (2136)	610 (389)

(ϵ^a) = molar extinction coefficient in $\text{cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

of low intensity is unexpected and can be assigned to intra ligand charge transfer transitions.

TGA/DTA : The thermogravimetric curves of the compounds were recorded in the temperature range of 35–800°C. The TGA curves of all the complexes are almost similar and indicate a continuous wt. loss till a stable metal oxide, WO₂ is formed. The decomposition of the complexes is completed in two steps. In the first step of decomposition, an initial wt. loss corresponding to loss of one thiocyanato group is observed at a temperature range of 177–182°C. Another thiocyanato group is lost around 218–222°C where the first decomposition step is completed. Second step starts with the loss of urea or thiourea around 245–255°C and weight loss corresponding to loss of N-methyloxazine or N-methyl-2,3,4-trihydropyridine is observed at the completion of second decomposition step around 635–690°C. Thereafter, on further increasing the temperature no wt. loss takes place due to the formation of stable metal oxide, WO₂.

Coats-Redfern methods⁷ have been used for finding the

kinetic parameters of the complexes. The fractional weight loss and the corresponding $(1-\alpha)^n$ values have been calculated from the TG curves at different temperatures, where n depends upon the reaction model and $\alpha = (w_0 - w_t)/(w_0 - w_f)$. The weighted least square method (LSM) was used for obtaining the best-fit linear plots and kinetic parameters were calculated. The decomposition of all the complexes have been observed to follow first order kinetics, as is evident from the linear plot of $-\log [-\log (1-\alpha)/T^2]$ vs $1/T$. The value of intercept, slope and activation energy (E) were obtained from the plots. The value of frequency factor (Z) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) as calculated from the equations.

$$\text{Intercept} = \log ZR/\beta E$$

$$\text{and } (\Delta S^*) = 2.303R \log Zh/kT$$

where k is Boltzmann constant, h the Planks constant, T the peak temperature and β the heating rate. The thermoanalytical data of all the complexes is given in Table 3. Thus, the overall thermogravimetric results support the conclu-

Table 3. Thermal gravimetric analysis of dioxotungsten(VI) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Dec. temp. (°C)	Wt. loss Found (Calcd.) %	Residue compound	% wt. Found (Calcd.)	E^* KJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^*$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
1.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMU]	660	56.18 (56.04)	WO ₂	43.82 (43.96)	76.58	143.49	289.20
2.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ MMTU]	645	57.57 (57.43)	WO ₂	42.43 (42.57)	88.07	151.12	296.64
3.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMU]	690	55.82 (55.86)	WO ₂	44.18 (44.14)	38.29	204.00	308.61
4.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PMTU]	680	57.32 (57.27)	WO ₂	42.68 (42.73)	26.80	149.94	312.29
5.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMU]	655	54.79 (54.56)	WO ₂	45.20 (45.44)	23.90	184.69	300.62
6.	[WO ₂ (SCN) ₂ PyIMTU]	635	56.14 (56.04)	WO ₂	43.86 (43.96)	47.86	150.40	307.60

sion derived from spectral studies as given above.

Based on the above observations, it is proposed that these complexes are of general composition, [WO₂(NCS)₂L-L] (where L-L = MMU, MMTU, PMU, PMTU, PyIMU and PyIMTU). The representative structure proposed for the complex is as

where L-L = MMU, MMTU, PMU, PMTU, PyIMU and PyIMTU

Experimental

Morpholine (Fluka), piperidine (SDS) and pyrrolidine (Fluka) were purified by distillation after keeping these bases over potassium hydroxide over night. Urea (Merck), thiourea (Ranbaxy), formaldehyde (Qualigens) and sodium tungstate dihydrate (Sisco-Chem-Industries, Mumbai) were used as supplied. The ligands were prepared by reported methods⁴. The analysis of tungsten was carried out by reported method⁸. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulfur analyses were performed by microanalytical methods. Molar conductivity in DMF (10⁻³ M) at room temperature was measured by Elico conductivity bridge type CM82T having conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.74. IR spectra of the complexes over the region 4000–400 cm⁻¹ were recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer-vector-22 using KBr

disc. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTA) of the complexes were recorded on DTG 60 thermoanalyser at a heating rate of 15°C/min.

Preparation of complexes :

Sodium tungstate dihydrate (1.2 g, 0.00363 mol) and ammonium thiocyanate (2.9 g, 0.038 mol) were dissolved in water (30 ml) at room temperature and 7.5 ml of 11 M HCl was added to it. The resulting yellow solution was cooled in an ice bath and ethanolic solution (10 ml) of ligand (0.00363 mol), MMU (0.577 g), MMTU (0.636 g), PMU (0.570 g), PMTU (0.628 g), PyIMU (0.519 g) or PyIMTU (0.566 g) was added to it. The reaction mixture was left undisturbed for about one hour in the ice bath. The precipitates so formed were filtered under suction, washed 3 to 4 times with water containing few drops of HCl and dried in vacuo.

where L-L = MMU, MMTU, PMU, PMTU, PyIMU and PyIMTU.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.S.P.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of teacher fellowship under FIP Scheme.

References

1. M. G. Drew, G. W. A. Fowles, D. A. Rice and K. J. Stanton, *J. Chem. Commun.*, 1974, 1125; C. A. Rice, P. M. H. Kroneck and J. I. Spence, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 1996; K. Yamanouchi and S. Yamada, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, **11**, 223; 1975, **12**, 9; A. Syamal and M. R. Maurya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 934; S. B. Yu and R. H. Holm, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 4385; M. R. Maurya, D. C. Antony, S. Gopinathan, V. G. Puranik, S. S. Tavale and C. Gopinathan, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1995, **68**, 2847.
2. R. C. Maurya, R. Verma and B. Shukla, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 730; R. C. Maurya, H. Singh, A. Panday and T. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1053.
3. B. J. Brisdon and D. A. Edwards, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1974, **10**, 301.
4. M. Ramalingam and D. Venkappaya, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1984, **56**, 2; A. Sabstiyam and D. Venkappaya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 16; M. J. Chebeland, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 101; J. Howatson and D. M. Gver, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1933; V. C. Asellato, P. A. Vigato and R. M. Videli, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **26**, 85; H. N. Sheikh, B. L. Kalsotra and Khema Shree, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 909.
5. A. O. Rajan, S. Adhikari and A. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 377.
6. A. C. Hazell, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1963, 5745.
7. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68.
8. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., 1968, 567.